

Preliminary results of the PEP4LEP project in Mozambique: Comparing the effectiveness and feasibility of a skin camp intervention to a health centre-based intervention for SDR- PEP administration

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Introduction

Leprosy is a chronic infectious disease caused by *Mycobacterium leprae*. The **PEP4LEP** project will compare two **integrated skin screening** interventions combined with the delivery of a single dose of rifampicin as post-exposure prophylaxis (**SDR-PEP**) to contacts of leprosy patients in **Ethiopia, Mozambique, and Tanzania** (1).

1. Schoenmakers, et al. "PEP4LEP study protocol: integrated skin screening and SDR-PEP administration for leprosy prevention: comparing the effectiveness and feasibility of a community-based intervention to a health centre-based intervention in Ethiopia, Mozambique and Tanzania." *BMJ open* 11.8 (2021): e046125.

Study flow-chart

Per country:

Skin camp intervention:

90 index patients

9000 contacts

Health centre intervention:

135 index patients

810 contacts

Objective of this presentation

Present preliminary results on the implementation of the PEP4LEP project in the districts of Murrupula, Meconta, and Mogovolas in Nampula province in northern Mozambique.

<https://leprosyreview.org/article/93/3/20-22016>

Schoenmakers, A., et al. "PEP4LEP study protocol: integrated skin screening and SDR-PEP administration for leprosy prevention: comparing the effectiveness and feasibility of a community-based intervention to a health centre-based intervention in Ethiopia, Mozambique and Tanzania." *BMJ open* 11.8 (2021): e046125.

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Methods

Between October 2018 and September 2022:

- Two training and refresh sessions were held with 44 health workers and 66 community volunteers
- Index patients and their contacts were included in both interventions
- Standardized interview & other data collection forms were used
- Afterwards, data is entered in RedCap (Research Electronic Data Capture)
- Skin Camp team: (1) general practitioner, (1) dermatologist (sometimes remotely), (3) health technicians, and (1) research assistant

Health centre based intervention

- 112 index patients
- 395 contacts traced/screened (3.5 contacts per index patient)
- 376 of 395 (95.2%) contacts received SDR-PEP
 - Ineligibility: pregnancy, age <2 years, etc. (1,2)
- Only two contacts refused rifampicin
- 29 Contacts were diagnosed with skin conditions

1. Schoenmakers, et al. "PEP4LEP study protocol: integrated skin screening and SDR-PEP administration for leprosy prevention: comparing the effectiveness and feasibility of a community-based intervention to a health centre-based intervention in Ethiopia, Mozambique and Tanzania." *BMJ open* 11.8 (2021): e046125.
2. World Health Organization . *Guidelines for the diagnosis, treatment and prevention of leprosy*. New Delhi: World Health Organization, 2018.

Skin camp intervention

- 56 index patients
- 3,665 contacts traced (65 contacts per index patient)
- 3,283 of 3,665 (89.6%) received SDR-PEP
- 1,847 of 3,665 (50.4%) contacts were diagnosed with other skin conditions and received free treatment or were referred to the referral hospital
 - Scabies, pruritic papular eruption, pityriasis versicolor, psoriasis, vitiligo etc.

New leprosy patients detected via PEP4LEP Mozambique

72 New leprosy patients were diagnosed, 16 (22.2%) were <15 years old

- 50, 69.4% via skin camps
- 22, 30.6% via health centres
 - 1 patient with G2D

Limitations

- A delay caused by COVID-19
- The lack of topical medications in the context of the treatment of mass dermatological diseases (e.g. scabies outbreak)
- Long distances need to be covered by volunteers and patients, mainly in the health centre intervention
- A higher number of community members are visiting the skin camps than the invited target group
- Discontinuation of medication for the treatment of leprosy (MDT shortage) in Mozambique and rifampicin shortages at global level

Conclusion

Despite the difficulties because of COVID-19, the PEP4LEP project is well underway in Mozambique, finding new leprosy patients and many patients with skin diseases in both interventions.

- The implementation of the project brought dermatological health services closer to the population
- It promoted education for the prevention of diseases, such as scabies & leprosy, in the community
- The project supports the health service (e.g. health worker training, medication supply) of the included districts

Thank you to the study participants, health workers, consortium staff & funders

PEP4LEP PEP4LEP: IMPLEMENTATION TRIAL ON SKIN SCREENING AND RIFAMPICIN AS POST-EXPOSURE PROPHYLAXIS FOR CONTACTS OF PEOPLE AFFECTED BY LEPROSY IN ETHIOPIA, MOZAMBIQUE AND TANZANIA.

Funders:

The image displays a collection of logos for the project's funders and partners. On the left, there are logos for NLR (National Leprosy Reference Laboratory), DAHW (German Development Cooperation), Erasmus MC (Erasmus University Medical Center Rotterdam), Ahri (African Health Research Institute), the Ministry of Health of Ethiopia, the Ministry of Health of Mozambique, and the Ministry of Health of Tanzania. On the right, there are logos for EDCTP (European Development Cooperation Technical Programme) and the Leprosy Research Initiative (LRI). The EDCTP logo includes the text 'This project is part of the EDCTP2 programme supported by the European Union (grant number RIA2017NIM-1839-PEP4LEP)'. The LRI logo includes the text 'This project received funding from the Leprosy Research Initiative (LRI; www.leprosyresearch.org) under LRI grant number 707.19.58.'.

EDCTP
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LEPROSY RESEARCH INITIATIVE
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Many Thanks

